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Efficient synthesis of novel functionalized pyrazolo-pyranoquinoline and tetrahydrodibenzo-[1,8]naphthyridinone derivatives

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Abstract

The facile and efficient synthesis of 1,4-dihydropyrazolo-pyrano-[2,3-*b*]quinoline derivatives from the reaction of 2-chloroquinoline-3-carbaldehydes and pyrazolones is described. Moreover, a one-pot method for the development of functionalized tetrahydrodibenzo[*b,g*][1,8]naphthyridinone derivatives is reported by using a three-component reaction of 2-chloroquinoline 3-carbaldehydes, pyrazolone, and enamines catalyzed by L-proline in EtOH.

Keywords: Multicomponent reaction, 2-chloroquinoline 3-carbaldehyde, pyrazolone derivatives, enamines, [1,8]naphthyridinone, organocatalyst.